

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, GA n. 871034

WP6 – MS12

Interim Report on Exploitation

Lead Author: Demetrios Anglos

Co-authors: Marta Castillejo, Paula Carmona, Adam Gibson, Roxana Radvan, Joseph Padfield, Sophia Sotiropoulou

Due 30 September 2022

Table of Contents

IPERION HS	1
Introduction	3
E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem	3
Exploitation Plan. Objectives	5
Training of researchers	5
Central Liaison Office (CLO) for Innovation	6
Facilitating exploitation – Lowering barriers	6
Innovation radar	6
Collaboration with Industry	6
Concluding remarks. Further work	7
Useful References	8

Introduction

Innovation is an essential component of the strategic objectives of E-RIHS. It encompasses novel research actions, offer of unique access services and provision of smart tools. Exploiting innovation, for the benefit of the E-RIHS ecosystem and the society, requires a number of actions along the innovation chain, including the presence of an efficient monitoring and evaluation system, appropriate knowledge and technology transfer channels, proper IPR protection and management as well as efficient communication with key stakeholders both in the public and the private sectors. An overall systematic approach to the above will ensure success and sustainability of E-RIHS as an innovator and as a leader in the global HS landscape.

This document, WP06-MS12, Milestone 12, *“Interim Report on Exploitation”*, is elaborated in the context of project IPERION HS, WP-06: *Innovation and Exploitation*, Task 6.4: *Exploitation towards the E-RIHS*.

E-RIHS as an Innovation Ecosystem

E-RIHS constitutes a platform for interdisciplinary partnership with the aim to address major scientific and technical challenges in HS, often beyond the realm of pure science and technology. It allows access to state-of-the-art equipment and facilities, top-level expertise, data, archives and collections, in an innovative way. E-RIHS is open to collaboration with other RIs seeking to exchange best practices and take advantage of innovations deriving from other scientific fields. Furthermore, E-RIHS encourages and facilitates innovation through different types of collaboration and strategic partnerships (e.g. among providers, between providers and users, with industry, at global, EU or regional levels). A major ambition of E-RIHS is to promote a culture of innovation all across the spectrum of its research activities, in the access services provided, through its unique training activities and even at the management level, exploring new models for maximising the impact of HS research on scientific knowledge, technological know-how and socio-economic growth based on the sustainable use of cultural heritage.

An innovative concept in itself, E-RIHS will offer access to large-scale and medium-scale analytical facilities (FIXLAB), to an impressive array of advanced mobile analytical instrumentation (MOLAB), as well as to invaluable scientific datasets archived in knowledge repositories of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (ARCHLAB). In addition, it combines these services with unique expertise in designing or optimising sophisticated scientific investigations and proper approaches for analysis and interpretation, specific to the targeted object or material, revealing their complex microstructure and chemical composition, giving essential and invaluable insights into historical technologies, materials, alteration and degradation phenomena or authenticity. E-RIHS aims at growing opportunities for innovation by exploiting the prolific interaction and collaboration between providers and users through the provided TNA services, building also strong links with industrial partners and the broader heritage industry.

Significant innovations developed so far in the E-RIHS organizations have emerged over the past decade through a number of projects supported by the EC, including those related to RIs, as well as

relevant national initiatives. Most of these innovations (see E-RIHS-PP, D9.2 and also Fig. 1) may be classified as follows:

Research-based: novel analytical tools based on emerging technologies and cutting-edge engineering that allow to efficiently address or improve the characterization of heritage materials or structures

Heritage (Use)-led: new methodologies that enable a global, multi-parameter understanding of heritage objects

Access type: novel and efficient modes of access to analytical technologies (FIXLAB, MOLAB), physical archives (ARCHLAB) or online scientific data (DIGILAB) that increase opportunities for exchange, interaction and close cooperation among a broad spectrum of providers and user communities on a truly interdisciplinary basis

Knowledge spillover-technology transfer (primarily inward): adaptation of tools and methods from other fields and disciplines such as geosciences (GIS), biology and medicine (genetic methods, imaging), materials science and nanotechnology (new materials for conservation); mathematics and computer science (data handling and processing and data management)

Access policy: open data sharing and e-infrastructures that ensure sustainable, open digital archives through the development of research e-infrastructure computing facilities and e-services, cloud based services, data mining or other HS relevant services.

Figure 1: E-RIHS PP Innovation Survey results on most common areas where innovations are made

A profound point of strength of E-RIHS is the catalogue of TNA services, currently fully active in the context of IPERION HS, which encompasses a rich and broad variety of cutting-edge tools dedicated to provide unique services to diverse user communities. These tools include: Instruments and workstations; Techniques and methodologies; Integrated multi-technique methods; Interdisciplinary approaches for data processing and interpretation.

Given the current experience, it is evident that many more innovations can be developed through E-RIHS in additional areas producing, for example, non-economic, non-technological and social innovations. It is noted that the overall environment is favourable. At the present stage a number

of key RIs, aspiring to serve various heritage research communities are developing under the umbrella of ESFRI, including pan-European RIs in the SSH domain (DARIAH, CLARIN, ESS, SHARE, CESSDA), and E-RIHS.

Beyond the direct impacts related to increasing the quality and efficiency of scientific output in HS, E-RIHS activities are expected to provide further impacts benefitting the scientific community, sector operators and the public at large. Thus, Europeans, more broadly, and public services more specifically, will benefit from better access to non-technical knowledge, improved awareness and increased understanding of artistic and cultural assets. Finally, implementing various types of innovations in heritage institutions can enhance the access of citizens to culture, strengthen its message to society and generate positive impact on cultural tourism.

Further, with respect to the context of the HS-society interactions, as pointed out in the *Interim report on Innovation Strategy* (WP6, Task 6.1¹) new challenges might arise in relation to human wellbeing and mental health domains. Studies have shown that access to heritage sites can improve people's mental health and wellbeing and admittedly this has been especially brought to light during lockdowns and travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A rather small but active community of researchers has been working in areas of psychiatry and psychology, however interactions between them and mainstream Heritage Science are negligible if not zero. A new opportunity for E-RIHS might be to engage with scientists working in mental health and wellbeing, perhaps as part of a potential new user community.

Exploitation Plan. Objectives

It has been quite evident through surveys and interactions among partners in the E-RIHS community, that examples of innovative findings successfully exploited by E-RIHS partners are disproportionately few in comparison to the rich innovation potential demonstrated by the multitude of research achievements in HS. This is clearly a problem and suggests that there exist gaps that prevent exploitation and commercialization of innovation. To bridge these gaps a well-defined plan is needed that will offer methods and routes towards efficient exploitation of the E-RIHS innovation potential. Main components of such a plan will include a number of actions as detailed next.

Training of researchers

Of key importance is to ensure that researchers have the right support that will facilitate them to take innovation from the research laboratory to the Heritage Marketplace. This is not a straightforward process. Appropriate specialized training, particularly for young researchers, is essential for developing skills and competences that will facilitate them to understand and determine the innovation potential of an idea, a system, a method or a product, search for the right marketplace, identify opportunities and develop a plan for exploitation.

¹ A. Gibson, WP6-MS7 "Interim report on Innovation Strategy".

Central Liaison Office (CLO) for Innovation

In order to effectively monitor the innovation derived from E-RIHS it is essential to set up an internal mechanism that will liaise with local technology transfer offices (TTO) in the participating organizations which are in charge of assessing the innovation produced. It is important to establish ways for exchanging good practices within the E-RIHS ecosystem. Furthermore, certain procedures and methodologies should be introduced for monitoring all steps in the pipeline of innovation. This coordination role is proposed to be undertaken by the Central Liaison Office (CLO).

Facilitating exploitation – Lowering barriers

The Central Liaison Office (CLO) in collaboration with the TTOs of the involved partners (and national or international experts) will provide customized assistance and consultancy services to researchers in cases of exploitable innovation outcomes. An evaluation mechanism will be established by the CLO, to monitor progress, advice on key areas for development, indicate exploitation opportunities and suggest adjustments when things ‘go wrong’. Researcher teams will be encouraged to discuss with TT consultants concerning issues related to IPR management, business development, market analysis and funding opportunities. Through this process the involved parties will have the opportunity to recognize from the early phases the innovation potential of their work in relation to the HS market and decide on the appropriate exploitation routes and the related steps. In addition, the CLO will facilitate and enable contacts of the interested parties with investors and venture capital firms, organizing special “Innovation events” and establishing channels of communication.

Innovation radar

E-RIHS will set up a mechanism to exploit emerging opportunities. The priority assigned to different directions will depend on the evolving challenges but also on the current momentum and related potential (human resources and funding schemes). The radar will be a mechanism/tool that will detect emerging opportunities in terms of financing innovation, collaboration opportunities, funding schemes and encouraging synergies between stakeholders. All E-RIHS partners could contribute to this mechanism (likely in the form of an online repository) where they could submit their information on emerging opportunities so that all E-RIHS partners could have access to it.

It is of importance that the Innovation radar ‘scans’ not only the landscape within the E-RIHS ecosystem but a much broader range (for example, medical diagnostic technologies, automotive and aerospace, construction and buildings sector or forensics and environment) where relevant ideas and technologies grow. This way, it becomes possible to adapt new tools and methods and introduce them to heritage applications and then exploit them in the Heritage marketplace.

Collaboration with Industry

Industry is considered as a key player in the development and the future of RIs, and according to the Innovation Working Group (INNO WG) a “bi-directional” focus is put in all its activities on the improvement of the mutual cooperation between RIs and industry,² placing industry among the

² The Working Group on Innovation (INNO WG) was set-up in 2013 in order “to propose to the Forum the broad lines of a strategic plan for an industry-oriented cooperation” of the Research Infrastructures (RIs), ESFRI Scripta Volume III, Innovation-oriented cooperation of Research Infrastructures European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Innovation Working Group, ISBN PDF: 978-88-943243-1-0

three actors for enabling regional development. In the case of HS, such a multi-disciplinary domain with a multi-faceted field of applications, “Industry” may be considered with a wider view as anyone outside of pure academia with revenue/ commercial potential. In general, “application field” might be a more appropriate term than “industry” in the common point of view. Considering industry in a broader sense as revenue-driven commercial companies and/or organisations, museums or galleries, private companies of conservators-restorers, can be considered as specific “industries” in the culture heritage field. Obviously, there is a wide spectrum of what could be classed as industry for HS and therefore, large potential for E-RIHS industry users.

Concluding remarks. Further work

Innovation is an essential component of the strategic objectives of E-RIHS. It encompasses novel research actions, offer of unique access services and provision of smart tools. Exploiting innovation, for the benefit of the E-RIHS ecosystem and the society, requires a number of actions along the innovation chain, including the presence of an efficient monitoring and evaluation system, appropriate knowledge and technology transfer channels, proper IPR protection and efficient communication with key stakeholders both in the public and the private sectors.

An overall systematic approach to the above will ensure success and sustainability of E-RIHS as an innovator and as a leader in the global HS landscape. In this context, a number of key actions shall be needed, which include:

- Mapping of key achievements across IPERION HS (and more broadly E-RIHS)
- Enhancing /exploiting the potential for advanced access opportunities across E-RIHS (identifying gaps and creating opportunities)
- Engaging the User Communities cultivating a spirit of co-creation
- Monitoring Innovation (also identifying obstacles and inhibitors)
- Protection and management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

From an even broader perspective, Heritage Science can offer a complex but wide range of benefits. It is important to recognise and account for different types of values, including financial, human, public benefit as well as academic impact. So, as pointed out in WP6-MS7 “*Interim report on Innovation Strategy*”, a number of other, more general issues need to be addressed and understood, for example:

- Whom Heritage Science matters to and why.
- Facilitating Developing the perception of stakeholders so they understand where and how science can be used to do good.
- Demonstrating wider societal impacts of Heritage Science beyond just generation of new knowledge.
- Exploit proper pathways to communicate clearly with a wide range of audiences inside academia and outside.

Useful References

Chesbrough, H. (2006), *Open Business Models: How to Thrive in the New Innovation Landscape*. HBS Press. 2006. [ISBN 978-1422104279](#)

Curley M., Salmelin B. (2018) Openness to Innovation and Innovation Culture. In: *Open Innovation 2.0. Innovation, Technology, and Knowledge Management*. Springer, Cham., DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-62878-3_13](#)

Kowalska, M. and Targowski, P., (2019, December 23). Success stories: impact of 15 years of European Research Infrastructure Projects on Heritage Science (Version 2.71). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592059>

E-RIHS PP DOCUMENTS

<http://www.e-rihs.eu/>

- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D6.2 “Sustainability document for business plan”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.2 “Analysis of the Innovation Background”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.3 “Innovation Strategy”
- E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.4 “Innovation Agenda”

EU DOCUMENTS

- The 3 O’s policy - Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World, (2016) ISBN 978-92-79-57346-0, DOI: [10.2777/061652](#)
- G. Sonkoly and T. Vahtikari, *Innovation in Cultural Heritage - For an integrated European Research Policy*, European Union 2018, DOI:[10.2777/673069](#)
- Sustainable European Research Infrastructures – A call for action COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT— Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, 2017, PDF DOI:[10.2777/76269 KI-01-17-790-EN-N](#)
- J. Hrusak, A. Harrison and L. Lenoir (Eds), *ESFRI Scripta Volume II, Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures* ESFRI, Long-Term Sustainability Working Group, 2017, ISBN PDF: 978-88-901562-8-1
- *Radical Innovation: Humanities Research Crossing Knowledge Boundaries and Fostering Deep Change: D/2015/13.324/12*, Science Europe Scientific Committee for the Humanities, 2015

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) DOCUMENTS

<https://www.oecd.org/innovation/>

- OECD (2021), *OECD Science, Technology and Innovation Outlook 2021: Times of Crisis and Opportunity*, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/75f79015-en>
- OECD (2020), *The Digitalisation of Science, Technology and Innovation: Key Developments and Policies*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b9e4a2c0-en>